

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Striga root parasite – a problem of dryland rice in the African savanna environment

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Striga species destroyed large tracts of rice in a commercial mechanized scheme for dryland rice at Sirasso, northern Ivory Coast, in October 1976. The most frequent species was *Striga forbesii*, with pink flowers; the least frequent was

S. hermonthica, with violet flowers.

Large areas of rice were killed by flowering time. There was a gradient where plants were progressively less affected between the killed areas and remnant areas of healthy rice. At the time of rice maturity, the *Striga* was flowering and vigorous in the fringe areas of stunted rice but it had already matured and died in the areas where the rice was destroyed earlier in the season. *Striga* plants beyond affected areas were rare.

All varieties being grown – Moroberekan, Iguape Cateto, IRAT 13 (irradiated short mutant of 63-83),

IRAT 8 (Moroberekan 63-105), IRAT 10 (Lung-Sheng 63-104), and a sister line of IRAT 10 - were affected equally.

Striga is a common problem on maize and sorghum in the savanna areas of Africa, and it has previously been casually noted on rice. It now appears that *Striga* is more than just a curiosity in rice and that it can destroy large areas if dryland rice cultivation expands in the savanna.

Mechanized cultivation with combine harvesters might extensively spread the parasite's very small seeds. Experiments are required to determine if control is possible through land management, crop rotation, or herbicides. The extensive area of severe infestation offers the possibility of screening for varietal differences in reaction to *Striga* to determine if rice resistance could be a means of control. **WY**

Soil and crop management

Effect of *Azolla* as a green manure crop on rice yields in northeastern Thailand

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Plants of *Azolla pinnata* were collected from a natural habitat in a swampy area in northeast Thailand in the 1977 wet season. They were multiplied in tanks until sufficient stock was produced to seed the experimental plots at an inoculation rate of 312 kg/ha before rice is transplanted. Several treatments were applied to accelerate the growth of *Azolla* in the experimental lots (see table).

Azolla was incorporated into the soil as a green manure at 29 days after inoculation. No *Azolla* was incorporated in the check treatment. The objectives were to find the best method of multiplying *Azolla* in rice fields and to compare the effects of *Azolla* as a green manure with those of chemical fertilizers

on the yield of the variety RD 1.

Azolla was remarkably effective; RD1's yield response to it was greater than its

response to 37.5 kg inorganic N/ha (see table, treatments 5 and 6).

The extremely sandy soil at the

Effect of *Azolla* on rice yields.

Treatment no.	Treatments		Fresh wt of <i>Azolla</i> before planting (kg/ha)	Paddy yield ^b (t/ha)
	<i>Azolla</i>	Fertilizer ^a (kg/ha)		
1	None	0-30-25	-	2.6 c
2	None	18.75-30-25	-	2.8 c
3	None	37.5-30-25	-	2.9 bc
4	<i>Azolla</i> grown without fertilizer, and incorporated before transplanting	0-30-25	794	2.9 bc
5	<i>Azolla</i> grown with 30 and 25 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅ and K ₂ O fertilizer as basal application and incorporated in soil	0-0-0	11,450	3.5 a
6	<i>Azolla</i> grown with 30 kg/ha, P ₂ O ₅ split 3 times at 10-day intervals then incorporated in soil	0-0-25	18,919	3.5 a
7	<i>Azolla</i> not incorporated in soil but 30 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅ , split 3 times at 10-day intervals	0-0-25	18,606	2.6 c

^aFertilizer applied to plot on day before transplanting.

^bValues followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

^cNitrogen split equally between transplanting and panicle initiation stage.

experimental site seems to favor *Azolla* in two ways. First, fixation of soil phosphorus is negligible, which favors *Azolla* growth, because of low cation

exchange capacity. Second, the soil's coarse texture causes rapid nitrogen loss, whereas *Azolla* releases nitrogen slowly. The results suggest that the effect of

Azolla was more favorable than that of a basal and topdressing nitrogen treatment (which is ordinarily needed when chemical fertilizers are used). ❧

***Azotobacter* inoculation on rice crop**

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Seed or soil inoculation with *Azotobacter* is increasingly being used for higher crop production. Under certain ecological conditions, *Azotobacter* fixes atmospheric nitrogen and makes it available for plant growth. The yield performance of rice inoculated with *Azotobacter* was studied.

A field trial conducted from July to October 1976 used ADT 31; from

November 1976 to February 1977 IR20 was used. The treatments were 1) 25:50:50 kg NPK/ha, 2) 25:50:50 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* treatment, 3) 50:50:50 kg NPK/ha, 4) 50:50:50 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* treatment, 5) 75:50:50 kg NPK/ha, 6) 75:50:50 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* treatment, 7) 100:50:50 kg NPK/ha, 8) 100:50:50 kg NPK/ha + *Azotobacter* treatment, 9) *Azotobacter* treatment alone, and 10) the control (no nitrogen or *Azotobacter*). The paddy seed were treated at the rate of 600 g of *Azotobacter* culture/50 kg of seed, and the seedlings and soil were treated with 1.4 kg and 2.4 kg of *Azotobacter*/ha.

In the first trial, using ADT 31, the grain yield was significantly higher (5.6 t/ha) in the *Azotobacter* inoculation treatment with 75 kg N/ha. The *Azotobacter* application alone gave a yield of 5 t/ha, which is not statistically different from that of 25 kg N alone. During the pishanam season, the maximum grain yield, 5.2 t/ha, was recorded in the plots that received 100:50:50 kg NPK/ha with *Azotobacter* treatment. The results from both seasons show that *Azotobacter* inoculation will supplement 25 kg N/ha and thus reduce chemical fertilizer application by 25 kg N/ha. ❧

Rice-based cropping systems

Relative abundance of five rice stem borer species on each crop of a triple-rice pattern in Iloilo, Philippines

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With supplemental irrigation, three rice crops are being grown in low-lying fields of Iloilo, a rainfed-lowland rice area. Stem borer populations for the crop year 1975–76 were monitored on each crop (IR28) by dissecting deadhearts and whiteheads. Five species were recorded; the predominant species was the white stem borer *Tryporyza innotata* (see figure). The yellow stem borer *Typolyza incertulas*, second in abundance, was prominent on the first and third crops. The striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* was the third most abundant; its numbers declined, however, during the third rice crop. The pink stem borer *Sesamia inferens* was fourth most abundant and

the dark-headed stem borer *Chilo polychrysa* was fifth. As current IR rice varieties are only moderately resistant to

C. suppressalis, stem borer control in Iloilo will have to be based on insecticides. ❧

Relative abundance of five stem borer species on each crop of a triple-rice pattern in Iloilo, Philippines, 1976.